

ADJECTIVIZATION AS A MORPHOLOGICAL-SYNTACTIC METHOD OF WORD FORMATION

¹Ibraimov Kholboy Ibragimovich, ²Jumaeva Feruza Ruzikulovna

¹Director of UzNIIPN named after. Kary-Niyazi, Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

²Associate professor, Navoi State Pedagogical Institute

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10358937>

Abstract. *The purpose of the study is to compare and contrast how other parts of speech are transformed into adjectives in the Russian and Uzbek languages, focusing on one type of transposition known as adjectivization. The article examines different scientific research on adjectivization done by Russian and Uzbek scientists. Using a comparative approach, it was feasible to identify the semantic, grammatical, and functional characteristics of adjectivization in contemporary Russian and Uzbek.*

According to the study, adjectivization is more attributable to participles in the Russian language, whereas substantive adjectivization is the most effective method of transposition in Uzbek. Additionally, several particular ordinal numbers, some relative and indefinite pronouns, as well as the entire number “один” (“one”) can all be transformed into adjectives in the Russian language.

The author of the article conducted a statistical analysis of the explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language. As a result, it was discovered that adverbs, participles, some verb forms and gerunds can be turned into adjectives in Uzbek. Although adjectivization based on adverbs and participles is conceivable in the Uzbek language, it is not a productive subtype of conversion that accounts for the few instances of it. In the article, the author also focuses on the fact that onomatopoeic words are frequently used as adjectives in the Uzbek language.

Keywords: *transposition, adjectivization, adjective, participle, transition, noun, analysis, morphological features.*

Introduction. The development of signs for the manifestation of transitivity in the area of parts of speech that were previously partially described in the linguistic literature but systematized, clarified, and supplemented by V.N. Migirin, can be considered of high importance for the theory of transitivity at the level of morphology. The theory of transition was also developed by M.F. Lukin, N.A. Kalamova, E.P. Kalechits, A.Ya. Bauder, Yu.G. Skiba et.al.; however, many of the crucial questions still remain unsolved. [4; 5]

Uzbek linguists such as T. Turdiboev, G. Abdurakhmonov, A. Gulyamov, S. Oblokulov, Zh. Khamdamov, O. Kim, Z.S. Isokov, A.E. Botirova, A.B. Pardaev, S. Mamatkulov, Ya.D. Eltazarov, A. Begmatova, I.I. Rasulov et. al. widely studied the issue of transitivity as well as the classification of parts of speech. [4; 5]

The object of research. In the article we will examine the process of adjectivization on the base of materials of two languages: Russian and Uzbek.

Adjectives were the object of special study of Uzbek linguists, for instance, they were very actual in the monograph written in 1974 by M. Sadykova (“Prilagatelniye v sovremennom uzbekskom yazike” (“Adjectives in the modern Uzbek language”), in the candidate’s dissertation work of A.A. Aimurzaeva (“Substantivatsiya imyon prilagatelnikhi prichastiy v sovremennom karakalpakskom yazike” (“The substantivization of adjectives and participles in the modern Karakalpak language”)),

1985), in the doctoral dissertation of D.B. Seytkasymova (“Derivatsiya prilagatelnykh v karakalpakskom yazike” (“Derivation of adjectives in the Karakalpak language”), in the candidate’s thesis paper of Kh.A. Baimanov (2020) (“Funksionalno-semanticheskiye osobennosti kachestvennykh leksem, oboznachayushikh chelovecheskiy kharakter (na primere nemetskogo i uzbekskogo yazikov”) (“The functional-semantic features of qualitative lexemes denoting human character (on the example of German and Uzbek languages), in the candidate’s dissertation of M. Kuldoshev (1995) (“Produktivniye affiksi, obrazuyushiye prilagatelniye v sovremennom uzbekskom literaturnom yazike”) (Productive affixes forming adjectives in the modern Uzbek literary language”) etc. These scientific studies examined the lexical, morphological, grammatical and stylistic features of adjectives, as well as the characteristics of the adjective derivation. The key characteristics of adjectivization and substantivization of participles in the Russian and Uzbek languages are examined in the work by A. Begmatova from the perspective of comparative typological analysis. The author contends that while adjectivization is the most effective way of word formation (i.e., the morphological-syntactic method) in the Uzbek language, substantivization is one of the primary ways of word formation in the Russian language and is not inferior in intensity to adjectivization. [2]

Methods used in the research. Using a comparative approach, it was possible to identify the semantic, grammatical, and functional characteristics of adjectivization in contemporary Russian and Uzbek languages.

Adjectivization, or the formation of new adjectives as a result of transition to their class of words that innately belong to other parts of speech while maintaining their original plan of expression, is regarded as one of the productive ways to enrich the language and stimulate verbal communication.

The transition of words from different parts of speech into the class of adjectives without the need of special word-forming affixes is known as adjectivization (derived from Latin *adjectivum* – “adjective”).

The obtained results and their analysis.

In the modern Russian language, the following parts of speech turn to adjectives:

- 1) Participles: *неизменяемые слова, утомленный вид*
- 2) Adverbs: *душа нараспаику, волосы торчком, шапка набекрень*
- 3) Pronouns: *шахматист он никакой*
- 4) Numerals: *первый ученик в классе*

The primary verbal characteristics of participles, aspect, tense, and voice, are what define adjectivization in the Russian language. When this occurs, the roles of these grammatical categories are lost or altered.

There are two main types of adjectivization of participles.

First, the introduction of figurative lexical meanings in participles that are typical of qualitative adjectives, such as *блестящие способности, подавленное настроение, оживленная беседа, упавший голос* etc. may cause a semantic difference between the corresponding verb and the adverb. The semantic shift may have led to the introduction of grammatical and lexical word-formation characteristics of qualitative adjectives, such as the possibility to create the comparative and superlative forms: e.g. *более цветущий вид, самый выдающийся ученый*.

Secondly, adjectivization of participles can be based on a functional reconsideration of the aspectual meanings, tense and voice without a loss of connection with them; the past perfect

participles in the perfective aspect typically denote a state that occur in the result of a previous action e.g. *освещенные окна, промерзшая земля*, but the present participles in active and passive voices signify the ability to perform an action or be exposed to external influences (e.g. *вьющиеся растения, печатающее устройство, нержавеющая сталь*). [8]

According to I.K. Sazonova, the term “adjectivization” has two definitions: firstly, the transition of participles into adjectives as a result of changes in semantic properties and, secondly, the process of formation of special adjectival meanings [10, 93].

As stated by I.K. Sazonova, there are more than 280 participles with adjective potential, including the words *блестящий, воспитанный, выдающийся, избранный, любимый* and others. During the transition into adjectives, participles stop to denote actions and indicate a quality and features of an object: «потерянный взгляд», «застывший взор», «вызывающая походка» etc.

There are two types of adjectivization: complete and partial. Complete adjectivization means the complete transition of the participle into the adjective: «дремучий лес», «колючие ветви», «вопиющие сведения», «спелый виноград».

When a word is partially adjectivized, it can function as the adjective or the participle: «изысканные на ремонт средства» – «изысканные манеры», «опрокинутое ведро» – «опрокинутое лицо»; «знающий тайну человек» – «знающий специалист» etc. The result can be the formation of homonyms, the words that have completely different meanings but sound the same: *противник, рассеянный артиллерийским огнем, и рассеянный человек, избитые животные и избитые истины; жидкость, вылитая в сосуд, и девочка – вылитая мать; преграда, образованная обвалом, и образованная женщина* and others.

In the process of complete adjectivization, the participles can appear in three different ways: 1) literally (e.g., *обслуживающий персонал, знающий инженер, мыслящий человек*), 2) metaphorically (e.g., *увядший взор, говорящая кукла, разнузданный человек*), or 3) as a part of a term (e.g., *отравляющее вещество, орошаемое земледелие, меченые атомы, открытый слог*). The grammatical method of adjectivization is characterized by the major grammatical factors, and there are hardly any modifications in the meaning of the genuine word. This approach is exclusive to the participles with literal meanings.

In addition to participles, other parts of speech can also be classified as adjectives. In some contexts, certain pronouns and ordinal numerals can function as qualitative adjectives. For instance: *Год проходит и другой – нету вести никакой* (П.). – *Оратор я никакой, между двумя словами перерыв обеденный* (Гран.). Или: *Три клада всей жизни были мне отрада. И первый клад мой честь была* (П.). – *Вскоре мальчик стал первым учеником в классе*. [3]

V.G. Gak believes that adjectivization based on adverbs is challenging in the Russian language due to the morphological characteristics of the adjective (Gak, 1983). It is important to note that many words in the Russian language can serve as both the adverb (words denoting the qualities of actions) and the adjective (words denoting the qualities of objects). In this regard, we completely agree with the viewpoint presented in the textbook «Sovremenniy russkiy yazik» (“Modern Russian Language”) published by V.A. Beloshapkova, which holds the theory that adjectives only include lexemes that denote qualities of objects and, as a result, are only capable of defining nouns but not verbs. For this reason, words like «наперегонки» (*бег наперегонки и бежать наперегонки*), «ёжиком» (*волосы ёжиком и стричь ёжиком*), «вкрутую» (*яйцо вкрутую и варить вкрутую*) are not adjectives (Russian Dictionary, 1989). Adhering to this

position, we believe that cases of transition of adverbs into adjectives are absent in the Russian language.

We are going to look through some samples relevant to substantivization of adjectives on the base of the book “Slovar omonimov russkogo yazika” (“Dictionary of Homonyms of the Russian Language”) compiled by O.S. Akhmanova [1].

Substantive adjectivization

APASH (noun) - a person belonging to declassified groups or layers of the population; bandit, hooligan (in France):

Была убита наповал шальной пулей во время ссоры пьяных апашей...

APASH (adjective) - turned down and unfastened a collar; having such a collar (about a men's shirt).

Participial adjectivization

BYUSHIYSYA (participle) (breakable) – present participle of the word *bit'sya* (break).

BYUSHIYSYA (adjective) - fragile, easily breaking into pieces from any stroke, impact, pressure, etc.

Adverbial adjectivization

UDOBNO (adverb)

- adverb form of the adjective *udobniy*
- in the meaning of predicate: without causing any difficulties, painful sensations, etc.
- in the meaning of predicate: without violating decency, without making it difficult for anyone

UDOBNO (adjective)

a short form of the singular adjective *udobniy* in neuter gender

Adjectivization, used in the Russian language, is essentially the transfer of participles from the verb form to adjectives as a result of the participle losing its morphological characteristics.

In comparison to their semantic derivatives, the genuine participial forms are more abstract; when speaking of participles, speakers typically wonder who did the action and under what circumstances they did it (e.g., *отравленная вода – кем? когда? Для чего?*) (*poisoned water; by whom, when, for what purpose?*). However, when discussing participial semantic formations, such questions no longer arise (e.g., *отравляющие вещества - poisonous substances*); “the gradual attainment of quality” specifies the lexical meaning of a word, and the grammatical meaning of verbal process is reduced to a statement of the state where an object finds itself as a result of a performed action (or the action performed over it).

Compared to substantivization, adjectivization is less frequent, although it has advanced significantly in the Uzbek and Russian languages.

Both transient (syntactic) and permanent (morphological) adjectivization are possible. It is also likely to identify participles that have fully transformed into adjectives. Among them are the Old Russian forms e.g. *стоячий, бывальщый, зрельщый, будущий, прирожденный*.

Characteristic features of adjective include the following:

1) the absence of dependent words, which transforms the participle into an adjective when it is used in their place;

2) the use of words with figurative meanings and the instances in which the participle appears in terminological combinations.

3) When participles are transformed into qualitative adjectives, it becomes feasible to modify the word in degrees, form adverbs, and detect synonyms and antonyms.

In her monograph «Imya prilagatel'noye v sovremennom uzbekskom yazike» (“Adjective in the modern Uzbek language”) M. Sadykova thoroughly examined the use of words from other categories functioning as adjectives. Just as adjectives are used instead of nouns, words from other parts of speech (for example, nouns, participles, gerunds) can also be used instead of adjectives. Often nouns (words denoting the material of an object) act as determiners. For example, *chit ko'ylak, rezinka etik. Ikromjon... yog'och oyog'iga... suykalayotgan mushukning shikoyatli miyovlashiga loqayd qarab o'tiribdi* (Said Akhmad). Nouns are used in a figurative or emotionally expressive meaning and function as the attribute: *zahar odam, tilla bola, shakar qiz, kumush suv, zumrad yaproq* and others. Adjectives name an attribute of a noun and are used as the adjective: *kelishgan yigit, oqar suv*. [9]

The investigation of the Uzbek language's explanatory dictionary revealed that adjectivization is a common linguistic phenomenon in Uzbek. [11] Along with this we can assert that substantive adjectivization is the most productive form of transposition.

Of the 114 examined examples in the explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language, there were 101 examples that were relevant for the adjectivization of nouns. [11]

Noun: *Yoshini yashab, oshini oshagan. Uzoq umr ko'rgan, qari* (about a person).

Adjective: *Yosh odam. Yosh juvon. Yosh kelsa – ishga, qari kelsa – oshga*. (Proverb)

Adverbs can also function as adjectives in the Uzbek language: *ruscha kitob, oqilona maslahat*. Although adjectivization process based on adverbs is conceivable in the Uzbek language, it is not considered to be a productive subtype of conversion. That is the reason for not having too many samples of this category of words. There are six examples of adverbs that transformed into adjectives.

Adverb: *Fan-texnika jadal sur'atlar bilan rivojlanmoqda*.

Adjective: *Elmurod jadal ishi borday chiqib ketdi*.

There are 4 examples in the dictionary for the transposition of participles into adjectives.

Participle: *Nihoyat, ichki bir turtki, anglashilmas bir kuchning sexrli ta'siri ostida, g'ayrishuuriy ravishda orqasiga – qiz tomonga qayrildi*. (Oybek, “Tanlangan asarlar”)

Participle: *Maqtasa arziydigan yigit. O'rnak olsa arziydigan xo'jalik*.

Participle: *Birlashgan kuch – yengilmas*. (Proverb)

Adjective: *Hayotni qiyinchiliklar, muammolar oldida yengilmas kishilargina rivojlantira oladilar*. (O. Muminov, “Khiyobondagi uch uchrashuv”)

There are also 2 samples for the transposition of verb forms:

Har kim tama yo'lin tutsa agar pesh, Oqibat bir kuni bo'lg'usi darvesh (bo'lg'usi – will be: the future tense form of the verb *to be*)

Adjective: *Mohira og'zi qulog'ida, bo'lg'usi kelinini maqtadi*. (L. Tojjeva, “Mekhrim sizga, odamlar”)

Tanish is the name of the action, e.g. *Bir-biri-ni tanish. Oq-qorani tanish*.

Adjective: - *Ziyodilla tanish dalayo'ldan xayol surib borardi*. (H. Gulom, “Mash'al”) *Uning qo'lida Zulfiqorga tanish kichik xanjar yaltirab turardi*. (Mirmukhsin, “Me'mor”)

The dictionary provides only one sample for the transformation of the onomatopoeic word “gumbur” into the adjective: – *Mashina gumbur, – dedi Rajab aka. – Endi bu yog'i senga bog'liq, uka!* (K. Rakhim, “O'z kasbini sevgan yigit”)

In earlier research, we examined the transposition of the word “один” (“one”) in contemporary Russian and Uzbek languages that represents a syncretic unit possessing the features of different parts of speech: categorematic and functional. It should be noted that the same sorts of transposition of the word “один” (“one”) are observed in the examined languages: substantivization, adjectivization, pronominalization, adverbialization, and particularization [5, 249-253] The adjective form of the word “один” is also acceptable. For instance, in the Russian language: *В одно ухо вошло, в другое вышло*. In Uzbek: *Opasi bilan fe’li bir* (She and her sister have the same character).

Conclusion. The use of one linguistic unit (word, form, or construction) to perform the function of another linguistic unit is quite common in modern Russian and Uzbek languages. During the process of transposition, the genuine word’s semantics and grammatical features tend to change, moving it to a different lexico-grammatical class. According to this study, substantive adjectivization is the most productive type of transposition in the Uzbek language and adjectivization is peculiar to participles in Russian. There are no instances of adverbs transforming into adjectives in the Russian language. Although adjectivization based on adverbs and participles is possible in the Uzbek language, it is not a useful subtype of conversion.

Most often, adjectivation is characteristic of participles, in which it manifests itself in the loss or change of the functions of the grammatical categories of aspect, tense and voice, i.e. main verbal features.

Thus, adjectivation is a morphological-syntactic submethod of the non-morphological method of word formation. It is a special case of transposition. It represents a transition, mainly, of participles to the section of adjectives, due to the loss of the morphological features of the verb by the participle.

Adjectivation is a phenomenon less common in the Russian language than substantivization, but has received great development in the Russian language.

REFERENCES

1. Akhmanova O.S. *Slovaromonimovrusskogoyazika* (Dictionary of Homonyms of the Russian Language). – M., 1986, p 448
2. Begmatova A. *Transpozitsionniye vozmojnosti prichastiy v russkom I uzbekskom yazikakh* (Transpositional possibilities of participles in Russian and Uzbek languages) - file:///C:/20(1).pdf
3. Valgina N.S, Rozental D.E, Fomina M.I. 2002. *Sovremenniy russkiy yazik* (Modern Russian Language). <https://www.textologia.ru/russkiy/morfologia/imya-prilagatelnoe/perehod-slov-drugih-chastey-rechi-v-prilagatelnie/490/?q=463&n=490>
4. Jumaeva F.R, Miskinova G.M. 2021. *Transpozitsiya na urovne leksiko-grammaticeskikh razryadov vnutri chastey rechi* (Transposition at the level of lexical-grammatical categories within parts of speech). “Obrazovaniye I innovatsionniye issledovaniya” Journal, №3. Tashkent, p 15-20. <https://interscience.uz/index.php/home/article/view/126/83>
5. Jumaeva F.R. 2023. *Emigratsionniy transformatsionniy potentsial chislitelnogo “odin”* (Emmigrational-transformational potential of the numeral one). Scientific journal: “Uzbekiston milliy universiteti xabarlari”, №1/2/1. Tashkent, p 249-253

6. Jumaeva F.R. 2021. *Tipi transpozitsii chastey rechi v sovremennom rusском yazike* (The types of transpositions of parts of speech in contemporary Russian language). "Molodoy uchyoniy" Journal, №47, part 7. Kazan, p 468-472
7. Jumaeva F.R. 2021. *Inter'yektivatsiya kak odin iz tipov transpozitsii chastey rechi* (Interjectivization as one of the types of transposition of parts of speech). //Universum: filologiya I iskusstvovedeniye. №12 (90), p 15-19. <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/interektivatsiya-kak-odin-iz-tipov-transpozitsii-chastey-rechi/viewer>
8. Lopatin V.V. *Ad'yektivatsiya prichastiy v yeyo otnoshenii k slovoobrazovaniyu* (Adjectivization of participles in its relation to word formation). <https://www.dissercat.com/content/adektivirovannyye-realizatsii-prichastii-v-sovremennom-rusском-yazyke>
9. Sadykova M. 1974. *Khozirgi uzbek tilida sifat* (Adjective in the modern Uzbek language). Tashkent, p 128
10. https://n.ziyouz.com/books/uzbek_adabiy_tili/Maqsuda%20Sodiqova.%20Hozirgi%20o'zbek%20tilida%20sifat.pdf
11. Sazonova I.K. 1975. *Prichastiya v sisteme chastey rechi i leksiko-semanticheskaya derivatsiya* (Participle in the system of parts of speech and lexico-semantic derivation) // Voprosi yazikoznaniya. №6, p 87-98, <https://vja.ruslang.ru/archive/1975-6.pdf>
12. *Uzbek tilining izokhli lugati* (The explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language). 2020. Under the editorship of A. Madvaliev. Tashkent, p 680ъ
13. Ibragimovich Kh.I. Peculiarities of using credit-module technologies in the higher education system of Uzbekistan //Integration of science, education and practice. Scientific-methodical journal. - 2021. - P. 209-214.
14. Ibraimov Kh. "Theoretical and methodological basis of quality control and evaluation of education in higher education system." International journal of discourse on innovation, integration and education 1 (2020): 6-15.
15. Ibragimov, X., Abdullayeva Sh. "Pedagogika nazariyasi (darslik)." T.: Fan va texnologiya 288 (2008).
16. Ibraimov X.I., M.Quronov. Umumiy pedagogika (darslik). –T., "Shaffof", 2023, 416-bet.
17. Ibragimovich I. K. et al. PEDAGOGICAL ABILITIES OF A TEACHER, STRUCTURE AND DEVELOPMENT //湖南大学学报 (自然科学版). – 2021. – Т. 48. – №. 12.
18. Ибрагимов Х. И. ПЕДАГОГИКА И ВОСПИТАНИЕ //Экономика и социум. – 2021. – №. 1-1 (80). – С. 608-611.
19. Ibragimovich, Ibraimov Kholboy. "Intensive methods of teaching foreign languages at university." Вопросы науки и образования 27 (39) (2018): 78-80.
20. Ибраимов Х. И. Педагогические и психологические особенности обучения взрослых //Academy. – 2019. – №. 10 (49). – С. 39-41.
21. Ибрагимов Х. И. Организация самостоятельной работы студентов в условиях цифровизации вузовского образования //Наука и образование сегодня. – 2020. – №. 7 (54). – С. 74-75.